

Citizen Science training program

WEEK 2:

VECTOR AND RASTER
DATA

Quick re-cap of last week:

We can digitise shapefiles by tracing over a map.

This creates vector data.

This data is useful for creating different layers on a map, like stacked pieces of paper.

This only scratches the surface of G.I.S however!

This week:

You will learn that:

Vector data can have different properties. We exploit these properties to show spatial trends.

Vector data, if used correctly, can also create network data.

The cousin of vector data is raster data. It is very different.

Each of these data types have different advantages and disadvantages, and determine what we can do with our analysis.

Before we get to it, is important for you to understand why there is a difference

The world, as you know, is extremely complex.

We try to understand this complexity by collecting data about the world. Some data focuses on trends, some data focuses on specific objects. But **both** are geographic in nature as we are looking at an area, location of aspect of the spatial dimension.

But, the problem is that:

“the world is infinitely complex, but computer systems are finite”.

i.e. computer can only process basic representations about the world. So we have to break this down into different formats

Different aspects of the world

As geographers we are interested in trends i.e. how things change over space or time

Sometimes this will involve the change of specific **objects**.

Sometimes it will be looking at how specific factors **(fields)** change over time or vary across space.

Discrete objects and continuous fields:

The type of data we should use depends on what we are trying to accomplish...

In the ***discrete object*** view, the world is empty, except where it is occupied by objects with well-defined boundaries that are instances of generally recognized categories.

- Objects can be counted
- Objects have dimensionality: 0-dimension (points), 1-dimension (lines), 2-dimensions (areas)

Can you think of any examples (Hint - think last week)

Discrete objects and continuous fields:

The ***continuous field*** view represents the real world as a finite number of variables, each one defined at every possible position.

- Continuous fields can be distinguished by what varies, and how smoothly.

Can anyone think of any examples?

Therefore, as a general rule:

Vector data represents objects

Network data represents the processes of vector data

Raster data represents continuous fields

Raster and vector data

Are how we reduce the world in to something a computer can understand.

As we said before, the world is too complex for a computer to process.

That is why everything we do is a representation of the real world. That's what I was describing last week!

Vector data:

One method of storing geo-spatial data.

Uses X and Y coordinates to define the location of points, lines or polygons (think about the different data types you created last week)

Vector data therefore defines the centre or the edges of specific aspects of the world.

Such data is generally saved as a shapefile, or, .shp

Examples include...

As a society, we divide the world up in to different layers of geography. Think about it, counties, regions, North and South, Villages..

Each is a different scale of geography.

We can get Vector shapefiles for each different layer.

UK general election 2017

- Conservative
- Labour
- SNP
- Liberal Democrat
- DUP
- Sinn Fein
- Plaid Cymru
- Green
- Independent

EU ELECTION RESULTS 2014

Geography Selection Diagram

There are other levels of complexity to this.

As independent reading, I would encourage you to explore this further..

How does vector data work?

Vector data has attributes, i.e. an attribute table.

You will see this in the practical today.

The attribute table stores different information about each shapefile.

This can be information such as the population that live in the shapefile, the area of the shapefile, the X and Y coordinates of the shapefile, the country it is located in..

global_power_plant_database :: Features Total: 29910, Filtered: 29910, Selected: 0

	country	country_long	name	gppd_idnr	capacity_mw	latitude	longitude	primary_fuel	other_fuel1	otl
1	AFG	Afghanistan	Kajaki Hydroele...	GEODB0040538	33	32.322	65.119	Hydro		
2	AFG	Afghanistan	Mahipar Hydro...	GEODB0040541	66	34.556	69.4787	Hydro		
3	AFG	Afghanistan	Naghlu Dam Hy...	GEODB0040534	100	34.641	69.717	Hydro		
4	AFG	Afghanistan	Nangarhar (Dar...	GEODB0040536	11.55	34.4847	70.3633	Hydro		
5	AFG	Afghanistan	Northwest Kabu...	GEODB0040540	42	34.5638	69.1134	Gas		
6	AFG	Afghanistan	Pul-e-Khumri H...	GEODB0040537	6	35.9416	68.71	Hydro		
7	AFG	Afghanistan	Sarobi Dam Hy...	GEODB0040535	22	34.5865	69.7757	Hydro		
8	ALB	Albania	Bistrica 1	WRI1002169	27	39.9116	20.1047	Hydro		
9	ALB	Albania	Fierza	WRI1002170	500	42.2514	20.0431	Hydro		
10	ALB	Albania	Koman	WRI1002171	600	42.1033	19.8224	Hydro		
11	ALB	Albania	Lanabregas	WRI1002172	5	41.3428	19.8964	Hydro		
12	ALB	Albania	Shkopet	WRI1002173	24	41.6796	19.8305	Hydro		
13	ALB	Albania	Ulez	WRI1002174	25	41.6796	19.8936	Hydro		
14	ALB	Albania	Vau i Dijes	WRI1002175	250	42.0137	19.6359	Hydro		
15	ALB	Albania	Vlora	WRI1002176	98	40.4874	19.434	Other		

Show All Features

Raster data:

Completely different to vector data.

Raster data work on continuous principles. Therefore, a raster data set represents ONE variable.

It is not a geometric shape. Rather more, it is a **pixel**. This pixel has a value within certain bands.

A G.I.S system will colour a pixel depending on where it sits within this band.

Nominal scale data over a continuous scale

Mixed conifer

Douglas fir

Oak savannah

Grassland

Advantages and limitations:

Vector data:

Advantages:

Shows clear boundaries of features.

Able to hold a multitude of different values (attributes).

Can be expressed via point, line or polygon shapefiles.

Generally small file sizes:

Disadvantages:

Difficult to represent continuous data.

Time consuming to make

Subject to interpretation

Lengthy to attribute values to the shapefile

Advantages and limitations:

Raster data:

Advantages:

Continuous scale of data

Enables functions which would be otherwise impossible with vector data

Pixels (Picture Elements) work on a scale, unless defined by nominal values.

Disadvantages:

HUGE files sizes

Complex to capture (later lecture)

Not accurate (varying accuracy depending on the resolution)

Network data?

Network data is vector data that has a series of rules applied as to how the data should work.

For example, by setting a road shapefile to be one way, or by setting a river as flowing in to another.

This helps turn basic vector data in to some form of modelling.

This is a complex form of G.I.S we will not engage with in this module. Requires a distinctive knowledge of Standard Querying Language (SQL). I will be teaching you the basics in this practical.

Windows Explorer sidebar showing file system navigation:

- ★ Favorites
 - C:\Users\ujaval\Documents\
 - C:\Users\ujaval\Downloads
 - C:\Users\ujaval\Google Drive\
 - C:\Users\ujaval\projects\qgis-
- Home
- C:\
- Q:\
- GeoPackage
- SpatialLite
- PostGIS
- MSSQL

Layers panel showing the active layer:

- Street Centerlines
 -
 - ▶

QGIS Style Manager dialog for the 'Street_Centerlines' layer:

- Marker Line
 - Marker
 - Simple marker
- Rotation: 0.00 °
- Offset
 - x: 0.000000
 - y: 0.000000
 - Unit: Millimeter
- Anchor point: VCenter
- Anchor point: HCenter
- Marker selection grid:
 - filled_arrowhead (highlighted with a red circle)
- Enable layer:
- Draw effects:
- Live update:
- Apply

Summary:

Difference between vector, raster and network data.

Different functions can be completed with different data types.

You need to know the relative advantages and disadvantages

The type of data we use depends on the specific representation of the work we are trying to create.